

Contributions and Challenges of Academic Planning Units in Nigerian Public Universities: Implication for Making Decision by Universities' Administrators

Annotation:

This paper looked at the contributions of academic planning units in Nigerian public universities and the challenges the units are facing. Qualitative and quantitative data were used in the paper. The data were collected from an online publication and print materials. The paper depends on primary and secondary data. The paper identified programme development, academic brief development, programme accreditation, effective data management, timely annual report preparation and timely academic calendar planning as major contributions of academic planning units to the sustainable development of the universities. The paper also concluded that lack of ICT facilities, poor funding, lack of cooperation with other units in the universities and ineffective training and retraining programme are the challenges some academic planning units in Nigerian universities are faced with. For sound policy measures, implementation and solutions, the paper hereby recommended that since academic planning is playing a crucial role in the development of the universities, the universities administrators should make provision for a constant training programme for the planners, provide the units with adequate ICT facilities, sensitize other units in the universities on the need to cooperate with the academic units and increase the impress allocation to the units for the effective administration of the units.

Keywords:

Academic planning Unit, Public Universities, Planning.

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Introduction

The Nigerian university system in the early 1980s was engulfed with many challenges. Some of them include poor quality, inadequate infrastructural facilities, shortage of instructional resources, poor research, poor supervision, over-crowdedness, cultism, academic programme proliferation, uncoordinated programmes planning and industrial crisis which led to the unstable academic calendar, poor planning, poor data management, lack of academic planning.

To restore quality and normalcy in the Nigerian university system, the National Universities Commission (NUC) gave a directive for the establishment of an academic planning unit in each of the Nigerian universities. The National Universities Commission (NUC) on the realization of the need to put in place some management structure that would guide the orderly academic development of the University in performing its statutory functions of teaching, research and development, it proposed and established the Academic Planning Unit in Nigerian Universities in the early 1980s. The establishment

of the Academic Planning Units in Nigerian universities is a response to the need to coordinate and streamline the academic policies and activities arising from sudden and sometimes uncoordinated growth, development and proliferation of programmes and units in the university system (Abubakar, 2022; Ogunode & Musa, 2021).

The establishment of academic planning units has contributed positively to the development of universities in Nigeria. The introduction of the units has helped in the transformation of the universities in terms of academic planning and programme development. There are fewer research publications on the contributions of academic planning units to the development of universities in Nigeria. It is against this background that this paper is aimed to discuss the contributions of academic planning units to the development and sustainability of the Nigerian university system.

Purpose of the Paper

The objective of this paper is to discuss the contributions of academic planning units to the development and sustainability of the Nigerian university system. The sub-objectives include

1. Define the concept of the public university;
2. Define the concept of academic planning unit;
3. Identify the contributions of academic planning units to the development of universities in Nigeria;
4. Highlight the challenges facing academic planning units in Nigerian universities; and
5. To recommend possible solutions to the problems.

Theoretical Framework

The paper is anchored on system theory. The theory was developed by David Easton in 1953. This system views an administrative system as a sub-system of society. It looks at various parts of an administrative system and examines the interlinkages among the various parts. It analyses the dynamic interactions between the administrative system and its external environment. Easton (1967) observed that a system is like educational institutions (universities), and is made up of a combination of elements: inputs, conversion process, outputs and feedback.

The application of this theory is relevant to the university system because the university has an objective to achieve and the university has many faculties, departments and units such as academic planning units that will work together to attain the whole objectives of the university. Every department in the university may have its sub-goals but these sub-goals of the various departments tend towards the achievement of the central goals of the entire organisation and invariably, if there is a fault in one subsystem or department, it would affect the whole system. Therefore, the total performance of the subunits or departments affects the overall performance of the whole set-up. The systems approach helps in the identification and solution of specific organisational problems (Yalokwu, 2006). The academic planning unit is one of the units that need maximum attention in the university.

Concept of Public Universities

Public universities are universities owned by the government. Public universities are universities established to provide post-secondary education for Nigerians. Public universities are universities established by the act of parliament to serve the interest of the general public. Public universities deal with the provision of teaching, research and community services (Ogunode, 2020). The objectives of the universities in Nigerian higher education, including professional education have the following aims: the acquisition, development and inculcation of the proper value orientation for the survival of the individual and societies; the development of the intellectual capacities of individuals to understand and appreciate environment; the acquisition of both physical and intellectual skills which will enable

individuals to develop into useful members of the community; the acquisition of an overview of the local and external environments (FGN, 2014).

Public universities in Nigeria are grouped into federal and state-owned universities. The federal universities are owned by the federal government of Nigeria while the state universities are owned by the state government. The National Universities Commission supervises over 200 universities, consisting of 49 Federal owned, 59 State-owned and 111 privately owned institutions. The Nigerian universities have about 2.1 million students and a staff strength of about 170,000 non-teaching and 100,000 academic staffs (NUC, 2022a). The federal government of Nigeria established the National universities commission to oversee the external administration and supervision of all universities in Nigeria. The NUC is empowered by law to lay down Minimum Academic Standards (MAS) for universities in the Federation and to accredit their degree programs. This led to the preparation, with the use of experts, of the Minimum Academic Standards for the 17 disciplines taught in Nigerian Universities (NUC, 2022a; Punch, 2022a).

Concept of Academic Planning

The academic planning unit is an organized institution within the university system saddled with the responsibilities of data collection and programme accreditation. The academic planning unit is an establishment that connects the universities to the national universities commission in the area of supervision of programme planning and development. Bright, & Abdulganiyu (2015) viewed the Academic planning unit as an integral part of the Vice Chancellor's office. This unit caters for the most critical needs of the University. It takes charge of projecting the university's needs and responding to them appropriately through effective planning, delivering relevant programmes, evaluating the outcome of efforts and reporting that outcome back to stakeholders. An academic planning unit is very essential for the balanced growth and development of the university education system. Every academic planner, regardless of position, responds to the request from faculties, departments, units and the public. It is expected of him to meet the needs of the university and the public, as well as for effective management of the system. The academic planning unit makes this possible by taking cognizance of past challenges and experiences and by using a pragmatic approach to deal with those challenges through logical processes and procedures. The head of the Academic Planning Unit in most universities is a Director who reports to the Vice-Chancellor. In some universities, it is an arm of the registry. Whether it is an autonomous Division or part of the Registry, the function is still the same. For these functions to be carried out successfully, University Management staffed the Academic Planning Unit with a full complement of personnel to execute the various technical and coordination aspects of the job.

Career staff in the academic planning unit begins from assistant academic planning officer-7, academic planning officer-8, senior academic planning officer-9, principal academic planning officer-11, Assistant chief academic planning officer-12, chief academic planning officer-13, Deputy academic planning officer-14 and Director of academic planning officer -15.

The Academic Planning Unit plays a vital role in the successful conduct of university business. It must, therefore, be staffed with competent and result-oriented personnel to enable it to perform its functions effectively. The competence and sustainability of the staff are very important. It does not matter what structure the University wants the Unit to adopt; what matters is that the Unit has a better understanding of its functions and is properly organized to perform them effectively. As a guide on how its functions are to be carried out, the National Universities Commission published a management manual in 1996 in which it spelt out these functions as allocate planning, feedback planning, process planning, institutional planning, research, statistics and publication, and secretarial services.

The objectives of the Academic Planning Unit in public Universities include: ensuring the compliance of the university with the National Universities Commission (NUC) guidelines on academic matters;

ensuring the provision of conducive teaching, learning and research environment for staff and students; ensuring efficient and effective utilization of academic resources and; to enhance the conformity of the university with NUC and indeed international academic standards (Olubunmi, 2015). According to Olubunmi (2015) the specific functions of Academic Planning Unit: Quantity and quality control organ of the University; it receives academic matters and policies from NUC and uses same to guide and advise all appropriate sections of the University in implementing such matters and policies under the directive of the Vice Chancellor and University Senate; generation and storage of academic statistical data which concerns staff's and students' information for various departments, colleges and units in the university; Academic planning matters such as preparation of academic calendar etc; it works with the National Universities Commission (NUC) in facilitation of the accreditation of courses in the University; collaborations with the NUC to establish new programme(s) in the University; generation, interpretations and analyses of data for the University System Annual Review Meeting (USARM) which holds annually at NUC; the university involved the Directorate in the University strategic plan programme; provisions of guidance for the Curriculum Review Committee; the Directorate prepares the Teacher/student ratio and the carrying capacity to guide and advice the University Management on employment and students' intake into departments and colleges; preparation and revision of the Academic Brief of the University; enrolment, projections and determination of Full-Time Equivalent (FTE), to assist in search of fellowships, scholarship and external aids for staff to enhance teaching, research and development, guiding each unit on the operation of the University academic brief; study and analyze how the University and the units within it are complying with NUC's parameters for fund allocation; getting up-to-date, relevant and accurate data for processing and generating information to guide University Management for accurate and timely decision-making on University matters (e.g. staff and students' records, financial records, research output etc.) and Any other services that the Vice Chancellor or University Senate may direct (Olubunmi 2015).

Contributions of Academic Planning Units of Public Universities in Nigeria

In this paper, the following will be considered; programme development, academic brief development, programme accreditation, effective data management, timely annual report preparation and timely academic calendar planning as the contributions of academic planning units of public universities in Nigeria.

Programme Development

The establishment of academic planning units in the Nigerian university system has led to the fast development of various programmes in the universities. Academic planning units are saddled with the responsibilities of coordinating activities relating towards programme planning, and development and pushing for the accreditation of such programmes within the universities. The assignments have been effectively carried out by the various academic planning units within the Nigerian university system since their establishment. Adeola (2017) observed that the academic planning units in Nigerian universities have done well in the area of programme planning and development for the programme growth and development of the universities across the country, Musa (2015) and Jude (2017) submitted that the academic planning units in the Nigerian universities have played a substantial role in all aspects of the universities, especially in the areas of programme development. Ojo (2017) opined that if not for units like academic planning in the universities, it should have been very difficult for universities to develop their programmes.

Academic Brief Development

The academic planning units in Nigerian universities have contributed to the development and reviewing of the academic brief of the universities. Ogunode, Ndubuisi, & Terfa, (2021) stated that the academic brief contains all the academic programs the universities will be offering. The document is

expected to project the total number of academic staff, and non-academic staff that the university should have before commencing an academic program. The document also contains the quality and quantity of infrastructural facilities that must be provided before starting new programs at the university. The academic brief is an important document key to the growth and development of the university system in Nigeria. Faith (2015); Afolabi (2015) and Mathew (2016) agreed that academic planning units have done well in the review of the academic brief of universities in Nigeria.

Programme Accreditation

The establishment of academic planning units in Nigerian universities has led to effective programme accreditation exercises in majorities of the universities. The academic planning units in the universities are saddled with the responsibilities of handling programme resources verification and programme accreditation. Accreditation of academic programs is one of the quality assurance mechanisms initiated by the National Universities Commission (NUC) to regulate academic standards and enhance the quality of university education in Nigeria (Akpan, & Etor, 2018). According to Obadara & Alaka (2013), accreditation is a process that aids institutions in developing and sustaining effective educational programs and assuring the educational community, the general public and other organizations that the accredited institution has met a high standard of quality and effectiveness. It is a measure of the quality of academic programs on the acceptable minimum standard provided by the accrediting agency. Okebukola (2006) described accreditation as a process of examining the availability and adequacy of resources, and merit rating of resources and programs to enhance the quality of output. This means that accreditation involves the process of ensuring that curricula, physical facilities, personnel, funds and so on meet the needs of the university to achieve its stated philosophy and objectives. Hence, it is a measure of the quality of academic programs and it is aimed at strengthening academic programs for quality assurance and quality improvement.

The objectives of accreditation of higher institutions/programmes as outlined by the NUC (2012) in Akpan, & Etor, (2018) include.

1. To ensure that at least the minimum academic standards documents are attained, maintained and enhanced.
2. To assure employers and other members of the community that Nigerian graduates of all academic programmes have attained an acceptable level of competency in their areas of specialization.
3. To certify to the international community that the programmes offered in Nigerian universities are of a high standard and their graduates are adequate for employment and further studies.

The NUC (2012) in Akpan, & Etor, (2018) outlines the criteria for the accreditation of academic programmes to include: the philosophy and objectives of the programme, the curriculum, teaching staff (quality and quantity), students' admission and graduation requirements, standard of degree examination, financial support, the status of physical facilities, administration of the department and employers rating of graduates.

NUC Benchmark Minimum Academic Standards (BMAS) of 2007 stipulated the following teacher/students ratio: 1:20 in science; 1:15 in Engineering and technology; 1:10 in medicine, veterinary medicine and pharmacy, 1:15 in agricultural and environmental sciences and 1:30 in education, management science, social science, law and arts.

Staff-Rank Mixes and Ratios should be 20:35:45 guidelines, for Professor, Senior Lecturer and Lecturer I and below. Six (6) academic staff is required to mount or start a programme in which at least one should be a professor or reader (1), two (2) senior lecturers and three (3) lecturers in the cadre of LI or L2 and below.

National universities commission has approved new Core Curriculum and Minimum Academic Standards (CCMAS) for Nigerian Universities for the following; Veterinary Medicine, Social Sciences, Sciences, Pharmaceutical Science, Medicine and Dentistry, law, Environmental Sciences, Engineering and Technology, Education, Computing, Communication and Media Studies, Basic Medical Sciences, Arts, Architecture, Allied Health Sciences, Agriculture and Administration and Management Science. The academic units in Nigerian universities have tried in the area of programme accreditation and resources verification according to Jude (2015). He went further to observe that the activities and roles of academic planning in the programme development in the universities cannot be underestimated.

Effective Data Management

Academic planning units in Nigerian universities have helped in effective data generation, distribution and storage. Data collection, storage and distribution is a major functions of the academic planning units. These functions they have been doing without any problem. Every year academic planning units collect students' data, academic staff and non-academic staff data in the universities. These data are collated, computed and documented for planning purposes and to make decisions towards the growth and development of the universities. Mark (2016) and Jude (2016) acknowledge that the academic planning units have ensured effective data management in the university system in Nigeria.

Timely Annual Report Preparation

The academic planning units in Nigerian universities have contributed to the preparation and development of the universities' annual reports. Every year the universities are mandated to prepare a comprehensive report of all their activities and programme for the year and document them for verification and monitoring by supervisory authorities. The writing of this report is domicile in the academic planning unit. The academic planning units according to Jude (2016) and Ogunode & Musa (2021) have been writing this report timely and presenting it to the management every year. This development has helped to improve accountability and honesty in the management of Nigerian universities.

Academic Calendar Planning

Academic planning units in the universities have contributed to the planning and development of the academic calendar of the universities. Every year the academic planning units of universities through their directors plan the entire academic activities and programme of the universities and come up with an implementable draft which through their directors is presented to the universities senate for adjustment and approval.

Challenges facing Academic planning Units of Public Universities in Nigeria

There are many problems facing the academic planning units in Nigerian public universities. Some of the problems include; a lack of ICT facilities, poor funding, lack of cooperation with other units in the universities and ineffective training and retraining programme

Shortage of ICT facilities

Academic planning units of many public universities in Nigeria are faced with the problem of a shortage of ICT facilities. Ogunode, Musa, Abashi, Iroegbu, & James (2021) carried out a study on the investigation of challenges preventing Academic Planning Officers from using ICT in their offices. The result collected and analyze revealed inadequate ICT facilities, unstable power supply, unstable internet service, high cost of ICT facilities, poor computer Literacy among academic planning officers, poor implementation of ICT policies in the universities, poor maintenance culture among the academic planning officers, lack of technical support for repairs and maintenance of ICT facilities by universities technicians and poor ICT capacity development Programme for Academic planning officers are the challenges preventing effective utilization of ICT by academic planning officers in the universities in

Nigeria. Ogunode & Musa (2021) also posits that working tools are office resources that support the delivery of academic and non-academic services within educational institutions. The academic planning unit cannot effectively discharge its responsibilities without adequate working tools. Shortage of working tools is one of the major problems facing the academic planning unit of Nigerian universities. Many academic planning units across Nigerian higher institutions do not have adequate working tools. The working tools such as computers; printers, calculators and office cabinets are not adequate for the academic planning officers working in the units across the country. Ogunode & Abubakar (2021) observed that working tools or office equipment like Staplers, Eraser, Push-pin, Drawing pins (U.K)/ Thumbtack (U.S), Paper clips, Rubber stamps, Highlighter, Fountain pen, Pencil, Marker, Ballpoint, Bulldog clip, Tape dispenser, Pencil sharpener, Label, Glue, Scissors, Sticky notes, 4A Paper, Notebook, Envelope, Clipboard, Monitor, Computer, Keyboard, Folder, Fax, Filing cabinet, Telephone, Swivel chair, Desk, Wastebasket, printer and calculators are inadequate in many units in the universities across the country. The inability of academic planning units to have this equipment adequately is affecting the functions of the units.

Poor Funding

Poor funding is a major challenge in the administration of academic planning units in Nigerian universities. Academic planning units derive their allocation from the universities. Universities in Nigeria are underfunded and this has affected the funding of faculties, departments and units within the universities. Ogunode & Musa (2021) submitted that inadequate funding is one of the major challenges facing the academic planning units of Nigerian universities. The annual budgetary allocation for the unit administration and management is inadequate, and this is affecting the effective performance of the units in delivering its mandate in achieving the overall objectives of the university system.

Lack of Cooperation with other Units in the Universities

Academic planning units in majorities of universities do not receive maximum support to carry out their functions. Faculties, departments and other units in the universities do not know the functions and roles of academic planning units. Providing accurate data and information to the academic planning units is always full of problems for these units. Majorities of the units handle memos from the academic planning units with a lackadaisical attitude. Abubakar (2022) observes that during data collection exercises in most public universities, the academic planning unit is not given cooperation with other departments in the universities in terms of providing the data demanded by the academic planning unit. Ogunode & Musa (2021) established that the academic planning units lack cooperation from the other units and departments within the universities. The functions of the units make it a central unit that must work with other units within the university system. Many departments and units within the universities will not respond quickly to memos from the academic planning unit. Many units and departments of the universities will not provide maximum support for the activities of the unit by providing adequate and up-to-date data and information for the academic planning units to enable them to carry out their activities and function as the planning hub of the universities.

Ineffective Training and Retraining Programme

Due to poor funding of capacity building programmes in the universities especially the public universities. This makes it impossible for many public universities in Nigeria to constantly send academic planners for regular training and retraining programme to build their capacity in carrying out their work. Abubakar (2022) submitted that the Poor capacity development programme of academic planning officers is another challenge facing the unit. Unfortunately, most of the Universities authorities failed to give many workers in the academic planning units across the country the opportunities to attend constant training and retraining programme to develop their planning capacity, and this is affecting their productivity. Training and development is the key to the high performance of non-academic staff in Nigerian Universities. Many academic planners since joining their respective

universities have not been allowed to attend workshops or conferences. This has affected their performance because regular training and retraining programmes help to improve job performance. Ogunode & Musa (2021) observed that the poor capacity development programme of academic planning officers is another challenge facing the unit. Unfortunately, most of the school authorities failed to give many workers in the academic planning units across the country the opportunities to attend constant training and retraining programme to develop their planning capacity, and this is affecting their productivity. Training and development is the key to the high performance of non-academic staff in Nigerian Universities.

Recommendations and Conclusion

To solve the identified problems and to realize the objectives of the academic planning units, this paper suggested the following:

1. The university administrators should increase the budgetary allocation (impress) for the academic planning units to enable them effectively carry out their activities in the university system.
2. The university administrators should address the problems of shortage of ICT facilities by providing adequate working tools such as computers, printers, scanners, A4 papers, printers, calculators and office cabinets to the academic planning unit of the university.
3. The university administrators should organize seminars and sensitize the university community especially Units, departments and directories within the universities on the roles of academic planning and the need to cooperate with the units to develop the university.
4. More academic planners in universities should be sent for training and retraining programmes. This will help to improve their skills and method of data collection and planning.

In conclusion, the paper examined the contributions of academic planning units in Nigerian public universities and the challenges the units are facing. The programme development, academic brief development, programme accreditation, effective data management, timely annual report preparation and timely academic calendar planning are identified as the major contributions of academic planning units to the sustainable development and survival of public universities in Nigeria. The paper also concluded that lack of ICT facilities, poor funding, lack of cooperation with other units in the universities and ineffective training and retraining programme are the challenges some academic planning units in Nigerian universities are faced with. For sound policy measures and solutions implementation, the paper hereby recommended that since academic planning is playing a crucial role in the development of the universities, the universities administrators should make provision for a constant training programme for the planners, provide the units with adequate ICT facilities, sensitize other units in the universities on the need to cooperate with the academic units and increase the impress allocation to the units for the effective administration of the units.

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